

Presence of *Modiolus lulat* (Bivalvia, Mytilidae) in Guardias Viejas, El Ejido, Almería (Spain)

Presencia de *Modiolus lulat* (Bivalvia, Mytilidae) en Guardias Viejas, El Ejido, Almería (España)

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ABSTRACT

During a study of the mollusc fauna present on washed ashore in the Guardias Viejas area of Almería (Spain), a zone with significant Atlantic influence due to surface currents, a population of *Modiolus lulat* was discovered. Numerous specimens were collected, some complete with periostracum and byssus, and compared with specimens from the Calahonda-Calaburras area in Málaga and with specimens of *Modiolus barbatus* from the province of Almería. This is the first population of this African species, considered threatened in Andalusia, found further east than Málaga. This record increases the known distribution of the species in the Alboran Sea and is relevant for its conservation.

RESUMEN

Durante el estudio de la malacofauna presente en arribazón en Guardias Viejas, Almería (España), una zona a donde llega una importante influencia atlántica debido a la corriente superficial, ha sido hallada una población de *Modiolus lulat*. Se han recogido numerosos ejemplares, algunos completos con periostraco y biso, y se han comparado con ejemplares de la zona de Calahonda-Calaburras en Málaga y con ejemplares de *Modiolus barbatus* de la provincia de Almería. Se trata de de la primera población de esta especie de origen africano, considerada como amenazada en Andalucía, encontrada más al este de Málaga. Este registro aumenta la distribución de la especie en el mar de Alborán y es relevante para su conservación.

KEY WORDS: Mytilidae, *Modiolus lulat*, Alboran Sea, protected species.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mytilidae, *Modiolus lulat*, mar de Alborán, especie protegida.

The bivalve *Modiolus lulat* (Dautzenberg, 1891) is an African species of the family Mytilidae which reaches the Alboran Sea of the Mediterranean. The species was included by ADANSON (1757)

under the name “le Lulat” in his book “Histoire naturelle du Sénégal: coquillages”, providing interesting information about the shell and the animal and exquisite illustrations with details of the foot,

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Table I. Material studied of *Modiolus lulat* and *Modiolus barbatus*. The locality, province, geographic coordinates, date, collectors, whether the specimen is complete or has only one valve, height (maximum size from the umbo), length (perpendicular to height), width (the thickness of both valves), internal colour, the type of periostracum bristles and its maximum length are indicated. AL: province of Almería. MA: province of Málaga. Coll: collectors (SC: Soledad Callejón. SG: Serge Gofas. DM: Diego Moreno). 1 spm.: a complete specimen. 1 v.: one valve. * Measurements of the complete specimen estimated from a single valve.

Species	Localities	Coordinates (Datum ETRS89)	Date	Coll.	Specimen
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 spm.
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 spm.
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 spm.
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 spm.
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.8'N, 2°51.1'W	Nov. 2024	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.8'N, 2°51.1'W	Nov. 2024	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.8'N, 2°51.1'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Calaburras-Cabo Pino (MA)	36°29.2'N, 4°43.2'W	25/10/2004	SG-DM	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Calaburras-Cabo Pino	36°29.2'N, 4°43.2'W	25/10/2004	SG-DM	1 v
<i>M. lulat</i>	Calaburras-Cabo Pino	36°29.2'N, 4°43.2'W	25/10/2004	SG-DM	1 v
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Guardias Viejas (AL)	36°41.9'N, 2°51.4'W	Nov. 2023	SC	1 v
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Punta Entinas (AL)	36°40.2'N, 2°45.1'W	12/05/1993	DM	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Bajos Roquetas (AL)	36°47.2'N, 2°35.4'W	03/12/1993	DM	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Bajos Roquetas (AL)	36°47.2'N, 2°35.4'W	02/12/1993	DM	1 v
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Puntazo Cañarete (AL)	36°49.1'N, 2°32.0'W	01/04/1993	DM	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	La Térmica (AL)	36°49.3'N, 2°26.6'W	Aug. 1984	DM	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	El Corralete (AL)	36°43.6'N, 2°11.9'W	23/07/1994	DM	1 spm.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	El Corralete (AL)	36°43.5'N, 2°11.7'W	06/06/2001	DM	1 spec.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Punta Redonda (AL)	36°43.7'N, 2°09.5'W	03/02/2002	DM	1 spec.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Los Genoveses (AL)	36°44.4'N, 2°07.0'W	09/06/1992	DM	1 spec.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Piedra de Blas (AL)	36°55.8'N, 1°56.3'W	02/08/2011	DM	1 spec.
<i>M. barbatus</i>	Agua Amarga (AL)	36°56.2'N, 1°55.6'W	12/09/2020	DM	1 spec.

siphons and byssus. Dautzenberg described the species using material from Dakar, Senegal, kept Adanson's name for the specific name (DAUTZENBERG, 1891) and expanded the known distribution to other places on the west coast of Africa (DAUTZENBERG, 1910). The distribution of the species in Africa extends from Morocco (PASTEUR-HUMBERT, 1962) to Guinea-

Conakry and the Ivory Coast (COSEL & GOFAS, 2019). According to these authors, the record of the species in the Cape Verde archipelago (Dautzenberg, 1910) do not correspond to this species.

In the Alboran Sea, there are well-established populations of *M. lulat* in the western half of Málaga, in the Calaburras-Cabo Pino area, and isolated

Tabla I. Material estudiado de *Modiolus lulat* y *Modiolus barbatus*. Se indican la localidad, provincia, coordenadas geográficas, fecha, colectores, si el ejemplar está completo o consta de una sola valva, altura (diámetro máximo desde el umbo), longitud (perpendicular a la altura), anchura (grosor de ambas valvas), color interno, tipo de cerdas del periostraco y su longitud máxima. AL: provincia de Almería. MA: provincia de Málaga. Col.: colectores (SC: Soledad Callejón. SG: Serge Gofás. DM: Diego Moreno). 1 esp.: ejemplar completo. 1 v.: una valva. * Medidas del ejemplar completo estimadas a partir de una sola valva.

Height (mm)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Internal colour	Periostracum bristles	Max. length of periostracum hairs (mm)
32	16.0	16.0	Purple bands	Smooth	5.0
49	27.0	26.5	Purple bands	Smooth	5.0
58	27.0	27.0	Purple bands	—	3.0
72	32.0	32.5	Purple bands	Smooth	3.0
31	15.0	15.0*	Purple bands	—	—
32	16.0	16.0*	Purple bands	Smooth	4.5
49	22.5	25.0*	Purple bands	Smooth	5.0
51	23.0	25.2*	Purple bands	Smooth	3.5
72	30.0	33.4	Bands and other purple areas	—	—
84	36.0	38.0*	Purple bands	—	—
48	21.0	22.0*	Purple bands	Smooth	5.5
52	23.5	23.0*	Purple bands	Smooth	5.5
53	24.5	24.6*	Purple bands	Smooth	9.5
Average:	52.5	24.1	24.9		5.0
39	21.0	18.5	White with orange-violet juvenile zone	—	—
21	10.5	10.0*	Violet hues without bands	Serrated	4.0
26	14.0	13.0	White	Serrated	5.0
27	14.0	12.0	Whitish with violet juvenile area	Serrated	5.0
50	27.0	21.4*	White	Serrated	7.0
35	21.0	18.0	White	Serrated	10.0
17	11.0	9.0	Whitish	Serrated	2.5
13	8.0	6.7	Whitish with violet juvenile area	Serrated	2.0
23	15.0	11.5	Whitish with concentric violet tints	Serrated	6.5
14	9.0	7.0	Uniform pinkish white	Serrated	3.5
25	15.0	12.5	Uniform pinkish white	Serrated	4.0
13	8.0	6.2	Uniform purple	Serrated	2.0
24	15.0	14.0	Whitish with violet juvenile area	Serrated	5.0
Average:	25.2	14.5	12.3		4.7

specimens have been recorded in Benálmadena-Costa (RUEDA & SALAS, 1998; GARCÍA RASO ET AL., 2010; RUEDA ET AL., 2010). It has also been reported in Campo de Gibraltar, Cádiz, although without detailing localities (MUÑOZ FERRERA DE CASTRO, 2018).

This study provides data on the presence of *M. lulat* in the Guardias

Viejas area of El Ejido, Almería (Spain), the easternmost known location in the Mediterranean (geographic coordinates N36 41.9' W2 51.4' and N36 41.8' W2 51.1'). Both fresh, loose valves and complete specimens with byssus washed ashore were collected. The shells are attributable to the species *M. lulat* due to their large, elongated shape, with a very

prominent and angular dorsal margin and straight edges. The exterior is reddish brown with a brown periostracum with non-toothed hairs. The interior is pearly-whitish, with a broad purple band and a parallel lower ray of the same colour, diagnostic of the species as stated by RUEDA & SALAS (1998) and GOFAS ET AL. (2011).

Material of *M. lulat* from Guardias Viejas in Almería and Calaburras in Málaga (Table I, Fig. 1), and also specimens of the most common species of the genus in the Mediterranean, *Modiolus barbatus* (Linnaeus, 1758), from different localities in the province of Almería (Table I, Fig. 2), have been studied to confirm the morphological differences between them. The shell height of *M. lulat* reaches over 70 mm (maximum 84 mm), while the maximum height of *M. barbatus* specimens is 50 mm. The length of the valves in large specimens of the first species exceeds 30 mm and in the second, 20 mm. The shell of *M. lulat* is more elongated than that of *M. barbatus*, therefore the Height/Length ratio is generally greater than 2 in the first species and less than 2 in the second. Regarding the Length/Width ratio of specimens, in *M. lulat* it is generally less than 1, while in *M. barbatus* it is always greater, with an average of 1.19. Regarding the perio-

stracum, the specimens that preserve it well have serrated bristles in *M. barbatus* (Fig. 2J) whereas the bristles are simple and smooth in *M. lulat* (Fig. 1O), as described by GOFAS ET AL. (2011).

The locality studied in this work, Guardias Viejas in Almería, is located approximately 150 km east of the stations where *M. lulat* was previously known to occur on the Málaga coast. This represents a considerable advance towards the Mediterranean, which could have been favoured by the progressive increase in seawater surface temperature in recent years, a phenomenon that has been observed to promote a tropicalization of the biota in different Mediterranean basins, including the Alboran Sea (FRANCOUR ET AL., 1994; BIANCHI, 2007; REAL ET AL., 2021).

The species was included in the Red Book of Invertebrates of Andalusia in the category "In danger of extinction" (GOFAS & MORENO, 2008) and later in the Andalusian List of Wild Species under Special Protection Regime, LAESRPE (Decree 23/2012, of February 14, which regulates the conservation and sustainable use of wild flora and fauna and their habitats), so the existence of additional populations of *M. lulat* to those already known in Malaga could guarantee its survival in the Alboran Sea.

(Right page) Figure 1. *Modiolus lulat*, Guardias Viejas, Almería. A, B: left valve with very eroded periostracum (31 mm); C: right valve with very well-preserved periostracum (32 mm); D, E: right valve (49 mm); F-J: complete 58 mm specimen, showing the exterior of the left valve, the interior of the right valve, dorsal and ventral views, and the umbo area; K, L: left and right valves (72 mm); M: detail of the umbo and ligament of the 58 mm specimen (from figures F-J); N: internal detail of a 32 mm left valve showing the two dorsal purple bands with pearly reflections; O: detail of the single hairs of the periostracum of the 32 mm specimen (from figure C); P: detail of the byssus of a 49 mm specimen.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. *Modiolus lulat*, Guardias Viejas, Almería. A, B: valva izquierda con periostraco muy erosionado (31 mm); C: valva derecha con periostraco muy bien conservado (32 mm); D, E: valva derecha (49 mm); F-J: ejemplar completo de 58 mm, que muestra el exterior de la valva izquierda, el interior de la valva derecha, vistas dorsal y ventral, y la zona del umbo; K, L: valvas izquierda y derecha (72 mm); M: detalle del umbo y el ligamento del ejemplar de 58 mm (de las figuras F-J); N: detalle interno de una valva izquierda de 32 mm que muestra las dos bandas dorsales púrpuras con reflejos nacarados; O: detalle de los pelos individuales del periostraco del ejemplar de 32 mm (de la figura C); P: detalle del biso de un ejemplar de 49 mm.

Figure 2. A-C. *Modiolus barbatus*, Guardias Viejas, Almería (Nov. 2023) (39 mm). A: exterior of the left valve; B: interior of the right valve; C: umbo area. D-J. *M. barbatus*, Punta Entinas, Almería (12/05/1993) (26 mm). D: exterior of the left valve; E: interior of the right valve; F, G: dorsal and ventral views of the complete specimen; H: umbo area; I: detail of the umbo and the ligament; J: detail of the serrated hairs of the periostracum.

Figura 2. A-C. *Modiolus barbatus*, Guardias Viejas, Almería (noviembre de 2023) (39 mm). A: exterior de la valva izquierda; B: interior de la valva derecha; C: zona del umbo. D-J. *M. barbatus*, Punta Entinas, Almería (12/05/1993) (26 mm). D: exterior de la valva izquierda; E: interior de la valva derecha; F, G: vistas dorsal y ventral del ejemplar completo; H: zona del umbo; I: detalle del umbo y del ligamento; J: detalle de los pelos serrados del periostraco.

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